

Methodology for the estimation of carbofuran in rice, wheat and water samples

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Manuscript received 10 October 2002, revised 13 August 2004, accepted 8 October 2004

A new method was developed for the isolation of carbofuran residues in rice, wheat and water samples. The method is based on the reaction of carbofuran phenol with *p*-aminoacetanilide, to produce yellow colour chromophore with an absorption maximum at 465 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range of 0.5 to 16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $2.177 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0102 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Carbofuran (2,3-dihydro-2,2-dimethyl-7-benzofuranyl methyl carbamate) belongs to the carbamate class of insecticides. In the last three decades, different laboratories worldwide have developed analytical techniques for the detection and determination of carbofuran and its metabolites in different matrices involving the use of GC, GLC and HPLC¹. Spectrophotometric methods^{2,3} have also been developed for the determination of carbofuran, most of them based on the previous alkaline hydrolysis of carbofuran to yield phenol. The present work describes the determination of carbofuran using diazotized *p*-aminoacetanilide as a coupling agent.

Experimental

Reagents :

(a) Carbofuran – analytical and technical grade sample (99.5%), supplied by Rallis India Ltd., Bangalore. (b) Stan-

dard carbofuran solution – 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ each in methanol. (c) Sodium nitrite, 0.5% (w/v) aqueous. (d) Sodium hydroxide, 2% (w/v) aqueous. (e) *p*-Aminoacetanilide solution, 0.1% (w/v) was prepared in hydrochloric acid.

Procedure :

Aliquots of standard carbofuran (0, 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 8.0 ml) pesticide solution were taken into a series of 25 ml standard flasks. To each one of these 2.5 ml of 2% sodium hydroxide, 2.4 ml of sodium nitrite and 2.0 ml of *p*-aminoacetanilide were added. The solutions were made upto the mark with distilled water. The resulting yellow coloured chromophore had a maximum absorption at 465 nm against a reagent blank and remain stable for more than 24 h. Absorbance values were recorded spectrophotometrically. The plot between concentration vs absorbance was linear over the composition studied.

HYDROLYSIS OF CARBOFURAN

COUPLING REACTION

Recovery of carbofuran from spiked grains : 100 g of each grains (rice and wheat) were spiked with 200 ml chloroform for 5 min. The samples were fortified with different concentrations of insecticide in methanol and blended for 3 min. Chloroform was filtered into 250 ml standard flask through Whatman No.1 filter paper and the residue was retained. The residue was washed twice with 10 ml chloroform and blended for 2 min. Chloroform extracts were combined and made upto the mark. Aliquots of (0.5–3.0 ml) the chloroform extracts were used for colour development after evaporating chloroform on a steam bath. The residue was dissolved in methanol and the amount was determined spectrophotometrically.

Determination of recovery in fortified water samples :

A volume of 1000 ml of water runoff was collected from different agricultural fields (rice and wheat) from Srikalahasti, Gudur, Nellore and Tirupati town. (Physico-chemical parameters of water samples : pH 7.0 ± 0.1 , total solids 50.0 ± 4.0 , DO 6.2 ± 0.05 , BOD 1.4 ± 0.05 , COD 13.6 ± 1.0 , phosphates 0.04 ± 0.01).

After collection of the water samples (minimum volume one litre) adjust the pH values below 4 with 20% sulphuric acid. Then fortify with different concentrations of insecticide dissolved in methanol. Next extract each sample in a 250 ml separating funnel with 100 ml of chloroform. Transfer the chloroform extract into a funnel and re-extract the aqueous phase twice with further 50 ml of chloroform. Add the second chloroform extract to the first and wash the combined extract with 0.1 M potassium carbonate solution, then dry the chloroform by passing it through anhydrous sodium sulphate in a filter funnel and collect the extract in a 250 ml flask. Concentrate the chloroform extract to 100 ml. Dissolve the residue in methanol and determine the amount spectrophotometrically as described earlier.

Results and discussion

The data presented in Table 1 and Table 2 suggest that the percentage of recovery from fortified water samples and grains ranges from 95.00% to 99.00%. It is evident that from the above tables that the proposed method is simple, rapid, sensitive and inexpensive. The data presented in Table 3 show that the active ingredient present in the formulations of carbofuran can be successfully determined spectrophotometrically using various reagents. The amount of carbofuran determined experimentally is very close to the manufacturer's specification and these are compared with those reported in the literature³. This observation suggests that the other ingredients present in the formulations

do not interfere. Hence, the method can be adopted for routine analysis of the purity of the commercial formulations.

Table 1. Recovery of carbofuran from fortified water samples

Sample	Fortification level	Tap water		Distilled water	
		Amount recovered	Recovery %	Amount recovered	Recovery %
Present method	0.5	0.48	96.0	0.48	96.0
	1.0	0.95	95.0	0.96	96.0
	1.5	1.48	97.8	1.93	96.5
	2.0	1.9	95.0	2.87	95.7
Handa ³	0.4	0.37	92.5	0.38	95.0
	0.6	0.58	97.0	0.57	95.8
	0.8	0.78	97.5	0.76	92.5
	1.0	0.91	91.0	0.93	93.0

Table 2. Recovery of carbofuran from grains

Sample	Fortification level, ppm	Carbofuran Recovery, %	
		Appaiah ²	Present method
Rice	0.5	98.33 \pm 0.2	98.5 \pm 1.4
	1.0	98.16 \pm 0.6	98.2 \pm 1.0
	1.5	95.83 \pm 0.5	96.7 \pm 0.9
	2.0	95.83 \pm 0.3	96.3 \pm 0.5
Wheat	0.5	99.00 \pm 0.1	99.0 \pm 1.2
	1.0	98.33 \pm 0.3	98.5 \pm 0.9
	1.5	97.75 \pm 0.2	97.8 \pm 0.7
	2.0	95.87 \pm 0.5	96.3 \pm 0.6

* Average of five determinations.

Table 3. Determination of carbofuran in insecticidal formulations

Sample no.	3% Granules	10% Formulations	50% Soluble powder	75% Wettable powder
1	2.88	9.62	48.66	73.75
2	2.89	9.68	49.00	72.50
3	2.91	9.66	48.66	73.33
4	2.92	9.59	48.83	73.75
5	2.72	9.85	49.33	73.75
6	2.90	9.71	48.88	73.96
7	2.91	9.73	48.88	74.28
8	2.89	9.81	48.50	74.06
Av	2.88	9.71	48.84	73.67
Rec, %	96	97	97.68	98.2
SD \pm	0.065	0.089	0.25	0.55

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to M/s Rallis India Ltd., Bangalore, for supplying the analytical and technical grade sample of carbofuran.

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